

INVESTIGATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL CYNICISM LEVELS OF THE PERSONNEL WORKING IN PRIVATE SPORTS FACILITIESⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to contribute to the solution of problems by determining the organizational cynicism levels of the personnel working in sports facilities which are part of the service sector in the globalizing world. The study was carried out for the purpose of determining organizational cynicism levels of employees in sports facilities and revealing differences between levels of organizational cynicism according to employee demographics. The study group consisted of 279 personnel working in private sports facilities in Istanbul province. Our study was carried out in the summer of 2016. A questionnaire consisting of socio-demographic data and a scale consisting of 3 sub-dimensions and 14 items adapted to Turkish by Arslan (2012) developed by Brandes (1997) for organizational cynicism was used. The scale was implemented previously by Mısırdalı Yangil, Baş and Aygün (2014) on the personnel who worked in starred hotels and a 14-item draft form was applied to measure the levels of organizational cynicism. Because the sample feature changed in our study, the scale was viewed with the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for the representation of the new sample group. In our study, age from the demographic variables was affecting affective and behavioral cynicism and seen the highest in the 20-24 age range. The cynicism levels of those who the employees who are married are lower than the cynicism levels of the single ones. Moreover, it was determined that the levels of

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behavioral and affective cynicism were lower in the employees without administrative duties, whereas there was no significant difference in the cognitive dimension. Despite the limitations of the research, it is expected that other studies will shed light on the determination of organizational cynicism levels in the sports field.

Keywords: cynicism, organizational cynicism, sports facilities, organization

1. Introduction

Organization is the whole of systems. As for sports facilities; they are the organizations at the forefront of the criteria that people take into consideration before or during sports activities, as a sub-branch of sports industry, which is developing rapidly. In other words, they are an institution or enterprise where sports are marketed and presented as a product. In recent years, especially the sports services combined with health, beauty, relaxation and recreation concepts, have created new opportunities and possibilities for businesses seeking to appeal to larger populations and to increase the number of members. Another characteristic of sports facilities is; face-to-face relations are intense as they are in other sectors (Ceyhun 2017). One of the important components of the service sector, human value, has become clearer in time (Çarıkçı and Oksay 2004). Therefore, continued performance of high performance employees of the sports facilities in the service sector will affect the performance of the enterprise. For the organization to reach its goals, it is necessary that the faith of individuals on the organization would be known as well as the value of human being come to the forefront. One of the increasingly important concepts in management science is cynicism (Mısırdalı Yangil F, Baş and Aygün 2013, Yıldız 2013).

2. Concept of Cynicism

Cynicism, in addition to being a large-scale concept, is the subject of different disciplines such as philosophy, religion, politics, sociology, psychology and management. Cynicism is the movement of thought and life philosophy, which the foundation is based in ancient Greece. Cynicism is considered as "*entities that are finicky, dissatisfied, constantly critical of events, opportunist and full of negative thoughts*". It also advocates that positive qualities such as honesty, justice and sincerity can be abandoned for individual interests (Efilti et al. 2008).

The individuals who believe that people are merely protecting their own interests and who think of everyone in the society as utilitarian are defined as 'cynic';

the view explaining this idea is defined as 'cynicism' (Erdost et al. 2007). The concepts of cynic and cynicism can be defined in the simplest form as that many people not trusting and disliking their circles and institutions (Brandes et al. 2008, Peng and Zhou 2009).

Cynicism is the mentality which believes that there is no good will on earth and that all behaviors are for own benefit of people (Erdost et al. 2007). Cynic individuals tend to have insulting and critical behaviors toward humans or society (Mısırdalı Yangil, Baş and Aygün 2013). Özgener et al. (2008) list some of the characteristics of cynics as follows;

- they see lying, attitudinizing and abusing others as the basic characteristics of humans,
- they act selfish when making choices, think their behaviors are unstable and they are unreliable,
- they believe that usually there are hidden motivations behind their actions,
- they may feel distress, disgust and embarrassment when they think of something related to psychological objects (person, organization, group, society),
- they can make criticisms with clear expressions regarding no honesty and sincerity in the psychological object.

Individuals with cynicism argue that organizing is coming to agreement, and that moving away from the self (Saruhan and Yıldız 2009). Cynicism affects not only the daily life of individuals but also their work life (Mısırdalı Yangil, Baş and Aygün 2013). It is seen in the literature that the concept of cynicism is handled in two different dimensions in the workplace. The first of these; "general (personality)" cynicism concept that reflects the individual's personality and perspective of life. The other is; "organizational" cynicism concept that leads to the formation of cynical attitudes in the individual and is based on organizational effects (Kabataş 2010, Erdost et al. 2007).

Organizational cynicism; is an academic concept that includes cynicism and types of cynicism in organizations (Akman 2015). According to James (2005), organizational cynicism is a reflection of the individual's negative thoughts on the organization and behaviors regarding the emotions. Organizational cynicism is the employee at the workplace belittling the management, accusing of selfishness, insincerity, believing that it lacks honesty and justice, and despising and humiliating his colleagues, taking a negative attitude towards the organizations of the employees. Therefore, behaviors include cynical and critical expressions towards the organization (Dean et al. 1998). Besides these, organizational cynicism is ongoing behaviors with anger, despair, disappointment (Özgener et al. 2008). These negative attitudes in personnel are observed as increase of disdain, condemnation, distress, sense of embarrassment, cynical humor and pessimistic thoughts (Akman 2015). Organizational

cynicism is not just about attitudes of employees regarding the organization, but also these attitudes with experiences (Johnson and O'Leary-Kelly 2003). Brown and Gregan (2008) also argued that the organizational cynicism is result of the experience of the person. In this way, they think they will experience exhaustion in the organization based on their bad experiences (Mahmood 2012). Dean, Brandes, Dharwadkar (1998) suggested that there are three negative dimensions, which the person obtains towards the organization he is working for.

- The belief that the organization is not honest,
- Negative feelings about the organization,
- They have described as insulting and critical behavior towards the organization in the direction of these beliefs and feelings.

The managers should take precautions accordingly by knowing the organizational cynicism levels of the employees before these problems arise and make corrections.

A. Cognitive Dimension

In this dimension, there are thoughts and beliefs that the organization is not honest. Individuals feel negative feelings such as disdain, anger, condemnation, insincerity. They think that the organization would use feelings like justice, honesty and sincerity in their own interests. For this reason, cynical individuals concentrate on their own organizational interests (Dean et al. 1998).

B. Affective Dimension

The feelings of anger, humiliation, embarrassment, pain and disgust that the sincere individuals feel when they think of organization constitute this dimension. That is, the affective dimension can be said to include negative attitudes and feelings (Dean et al. 1998).

C. Behavioral Dimension

In this last sub-dimension, the individual now begins to turn the negative emotions that he feels into behavior. Complains about the organization and makes pessimistic and negative predictions for future of the organization, displays cynical attitudes against his circles (Brandes et al. 2008).

Several factors are influential in the appearance of organizational cynicism. Turan ranked these factors as extreme stress and role load, inability to reach personal and organizational goals, lack of social support mechanisms, promotion not matching the effort made, conflict of goal, organizational complexity, inadequacy of decision making, communication problems, psychological pressure and laying off. (Turan 2011).

The purpose of this research is to contribute to the solution of problems by

determining the organizational cynicism levels of the personnel working in sports facilities which are part of the service sector in the globalizing world.

2. Material and Method

The study was carried out for the purpose of determining organizational cynicism levels of employees in sports facilities and revealing differences between levels of organizational cynicism according to employee demographics. Research conducted in the context of this purpose can be described as screening model. Screening model; is referred to research approaches trying to describe an existing situation as is (Karasar 2007).

2.1 Study Sample

The study group consisted of 279 personnel working in private sports facilities in Istanbul province. Our study was carried out in the summer of 2016. Data on socio-demographic variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Demographic Characteristics of Employees in Sports Facilities

Demographic Characteristics	Categories	f	%
Age Level	20-24	41	14,7
	25-30	57	20,4
	31-35	45	16,1
	36-40	40	14,3
	41-45	38	13,6
	46-50	33	11,8
	51 and over	25	9,0
Marital Status	Married	171	61,3
	Single	108	38,7
Status of Administrative Duty	Yes	132	47,3
	No	147	52,7
Occupational Working Year	Less than a Year	27	9,7
	1-5 Years	86	30,8
	6-10 Years	63	22,6
	11-15 Years	58	20,8
	16 and over	45	16,1
Monthly Income	0-1000 TL	32	11,5
	1001-2000 TL	67	24,0
	2001-3000 TL	83	29,7
	3001-4000 TL	71	25,4
	4001 and over	26	9,3
Total		279	100,0

2.2 Data Collection Tools

A questionnaire consisting of socio-demographic data and a scale consisting of 3 sub-dimensions and 14 items adapted to Turkish by Arslan (2012) developed by Brandes (1997) for organizational cynicisms were used. The scale was implemented previously by Mısırdalı Yangil, Baş and Aygün (2014) on the personnel who worked in starred hotels and a 14-item draft form was applied to measure the levels of organizational cynicism. Because the sample feature changed in our study, the scale was viewed with the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for the representation of the new sample group. CFA applied to the structure of organizational cynicism scale with 3 factors 14 items, was applied as a representative of structure validity. The analysis found that the 20. Item in the behavior sub-factor had a non-significant t value. This item was removed from the scale and the CFA model was re-established. When the t compliance statistics of the items of the CFA model established with 13 items were examined, it was determined that there were no incompatible substances. The resulting CFA model is given in Figure 1. Since the Relative Multivariate Kurtosis = 1.175 > 1.00, the assumption of multivariate normality is not satisfied and therefore the Robust Maximum Likelihood (RML) parameter estimation method is used instead of the Maximum Likelihood (ML) parameter estimation method. The compliance index values of Organizational Cynicism scale are given in Table 2.

Table 2: The Compliance Index Values of Validity Study of Organizational Cynicism Scale

Compliance Index	$\chi^2 / (df)$	RMSEA	SRMR	TLI/NNFI	CFI	NFI
	130.33/(58)=2.25	0.074	0.075	0.96	0.97	0.95

Since $2 < \chi^2 / (df) = 1.84 \leq 3$ is in range of critical values, it is seen to show acceptable compliance. The RMSEA and SRMR values are smaller than the critical value of 0.08, indicating that they have an acceptable compliance index (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). It is seen that CFI and NFI values have good compliance index values and TLI / NNFI values have an acceptable compliance index (Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). When the compliance index values were examined, it was seen that the sub-factors of the organizational cynicism scale and the measurement model established with the general were validated.

Figure 1: 1st Level 3 Factor CFA Model of Organizational Cynicism Scale

Internal consistency coefficient Cronbach alpha was calculated in determination of the reliability of the scale. The reliability coefficient of the Organizational Cynicism Scale overall was found to be 0.90. According to Özdamar (1999), the Cronbach Alpha reliability value being at 0.60 to 0.80 is considered to be reliable at acceptable level and highly reliable being at 0.80-0.90. In this context, it is shown in Table 3 that the reliability coefficients of the affective cynicism sub-factor have acceptable levels of reliability in the context of the sub-factors, and that the reliability coefficient of the cognitive and behavioral sub-factors and the scale has a high reliability coefficient.

Table 3: Cronbach Alpha Reliability Results of Generic and Sub Factors of Organizational Cynicism Scale

	Cognitive Cynicism	Behavioral Cynicism	Affective Cynicism	Organizational Cynicism
Number of items	5	4	4	13
Cronbach α	,88	,83	,67	,90

2.3 Data Analysis Techniques

First level 3 factor confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed using the LISREL package program to reveal the validation status of the new participant group. A decision was made on the validation status of the measurement scale by looking at the chi-square statistics, error indices (RMSEA, SRMR), compliance indices (NFI, NNFI, CFI). Cronbach Alpha reliability analysis was used to evaluate the reliability of the sub scales and the general of the scale. The normality of the point distributions obtained from the general and subscales of the scale was examined by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z test and its homogeneity was measured by the Levene Homogeneity test, that the p value obtained for all values is higher than the critical value of 0.05 and that the point distribution is normal and the test variances are homogeneous. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum value, maximum value, skewness and kurtosis) were calculated for the sub-factors of organizational cynicism scale and the distributions of points obtained from the general. The significance difference between the demographic characteristics of the employees and the cynicism levels related to the sub-factors and generalities of the organizational cynicism scale according to the status of the administrative duties was examined by the Independent-Sample t test analysis. One-Way ANOVA analysis was used to examine the significance of the differences in cynicism levels between organizational cynicism scale sub-factors and general cynicism according to age, occupational year and monthly income levels of employees.

3. Findings

3.1. Organizational Cynicism Levels of Personnel According to Sub Dimensions of Scale

Information on organizational cynicism levels of employees in sports facilities is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on Levels of Employees for General and Sub Factors of Organizational Cynicism Scale

Sub Dimensions	N	Minimum	Maximum	$\bar{X}$	S	Skewness	Kurtosis
Cognitive Cynicism	279	5,00	18,00	9,09	3,19	,49	-,13
Behavioral Cynicism	279	4,00	14,00	6,85	2,52	,77	-,19
Affective Cynicism	279	4,00	18,00	9,74	2,93	,05	-,51
Organizational Cynicism Level	279	13,00	46,00	25,47	6,75	,41	-,32

In the dimension of "cognitive cynicism"; it is seen that employees have an $\bar{X}=9,09$ (S = 3.19) levels of cynicism average. The cognitive cynicism levels of employees are found to have an average level with 49 skewness value. Cynicism levels of employees in "Behavioral Cynicism" dimension is seen to have $\bar{X}=6.85$ (S = 2.52) average. The behavioral cynicism levels of the employees seem to have a level below the average of 77 skewness value. Cynicism levels of the employees in the dimension of "Affective Cynicism" is seen to have $\bar{X}=9,74$ (S = 2.93) average. It is seen that the levels of cognitive cynicism of the employees have a level below the average with 0,05 skewness value. When we look at the general cynicism scale in general, it is seen that the level of employees has an average of $\bar{X}=25,47$ (S = 6.75). It is seen that the levels of organizational cynicism of the employees have a level below the average with 0,41 skewness value.

3.2. Levels of Cynicism According to Demographic Characteristics in Sports Facilities

3.2.1. Organizational Cynicism Levels of Employees in Sports Facilities by Age

Organizational cynicism levels of employees in sport facilities according to the age are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Cynicism Levels of Employees Related to Generic and Sub Factors of Organizational Cynicism by Age

Sub Dimensions	Age	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F(6-272)	p	Post Hoc (Tukey)
Cognitive Cynicism	20-24	41	9,59	3,57	,387	,887	
	25-30	57	8,82	3,06			
	31-35	45	9,44	3,47			
	36-40	40	8,98	3,17			
	41-45	38	8,97	3,04			
	46-50	33	8,82	2,92			
	51 and over	25	8,92	3,09			
Behavioral Cynicism	20-24	41	8,39	2,49	4,993	,000*	1>2, 1>3, 1>4, 1>7
	25-30	57	6,74	2,16			
	31-35	45	5,82	1,97			
	36-40	40	6,35	2,99			
	41-45	38	7,26	2,48			
	46-50	33	7,15	2,51			
	51 and over	25	6,20	2,38			
Affective Cynicism	20-24	41	11,85	2,66	5,894	,000*	1>2, 1>3, 1>4,
	25-30	57	9,98	2,91			

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Organizational Cynicism Level	31-35	45	9,11	2,85			1>5,
	36-40	40	8,70	2,96			1>6,
	41-45	38	9,84	2,82			1>7
	46-50	33	9,45	2,15			
	51 and over	25	8,76	2,99			
	20-24	41	30,83	6,00			
	25-30	57	25,68	6,14			1>2, 1>3, 1>4,
	31-35	45	23,58	6,41			1>5,
	36-40	40	23,78	7,42	6,831	,000*	1>6,
	41-45	38	25,76	6,27			1>7
46-50	33	24,76	6,36				
51 and over	25	22,76	5,64				

*p<,05 Categories: 20-24=1, 25-30=2, 31-35=3, 36-40=4, 41-45=5, 46-50=6, 51 and over=7

According to the age of employees of the sub-cognitive cynicism sub-factor, there is no significant difference in cynicism levels according to $F(6-272) = 39, p = ,887 > ,05$. It is seen that there is a significant difference between the levels of cynicism according to the age of employees regarding the "Behavioral Cynicism" sub-factor according to $F(6-272) = 4,99, p = ,000 < ,05$. It is seen that there is a significant difference between the levels of cynicism according to the age of employees related to "Affective Cynicism" sub-factor $F(6-272) = 5,89, p = ,000 < ,05$. It is seen that there is a significant difference between the levels of cynicism according to the age of employees in relation to the general organizational cynicism scale according to $F(6-272) = 6,83, p = ,000 < ,05$. This significant difference results from the fact that the organizational cynicism levels ($\bar{X} = 30,83$) of the employees who have "20-24" age level are higher than the other age groups.

3.2.2 Organizational Cynicism Levels of Employees in Sports Facilities by Marital Status

Organizational Cynicism Levels of Employees in Sports Facilities by Marital Status are given in Table 6.

Table 6: Independent-Sample T-Test Results of the Difference between Cynicism Levels of the General and Sub Factors of the Organizational Cynicism Scale by Marital Status of Employees

Sub Dimensions	Marital Status	N	$\bar{X}$	S	T	P
Cognitive Cynicism	Married	171	8,66	3,06	2,88	,004*
	Single	108	9,77	3,28		
Behavioral Cynicism	Married	171	6,67	2,59	1,53	,128
	Single	108	7,14	2,39		
Affective Cynicism	Married	171	9,31	2,80	3,15	,002*

Organizational Cynicism Level	Single	108	10,43	3,02	3,20	,002*
	Married	171	24,46	6,52		
	Single	108	27,06	6,84		

*p<,05

Significant difference was determined between the organizational cynicism levels of those married ($\bar{X}=8,66$) and single on "cognitive cynicism" sub factor ($\bar{X}=9,77$) according to $t_{(277)}=2,88$, $p=,004<,05$, between organizational cynicism levels of those married ($\bar{X}=9,31$) and single ($\bar{X}=10,43$) according to $t_{(277)}=3,15$, $p=,002<,05$. It was seen that there was no significant difference between organizational cynicism levels of those married ($\bar{X}=6,67$) and single ($\bar{X}=7,14$) in behavioral cynicism sub factor according to $t_{(277)}=1,53$, $p=,128>,05$. It was seen that there was no significant difference between organizational cynicism levels of those married ($\bar{X}=24,46$) and single ($\bar{X}=27,06$) in behavioral cynicism sub factor according to $t_{(277)}=3,20$, $p=,002<,05$.

When the scores obtained from the general of cognitive cynicism sub-factor, affective cynicism sub-factor and organizational cynicism scale, it is found that cynicism levels of those married are lower than cynicism levels of those single and that this difference is significant.

3.2.3 Levels of Cynicism of Employees in Sports Facilities on whether they have Administrative Duties

The difference between the organizational cynicism levels of employees in sport facilities according to whether they have an administrative duty are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Independent-Sample T-Test Results of Differences in Cynicism Levels According to the Administrative Duties Status of Employees

Sub Dimensions	Administrative Duty Status	N	$\bar{X}$	S	t	p
Cognitive Cynicism	Yes	132	8,98	3,03	,502	,616
	No	147	9,18	3,33		
Behavioral Cynicism	Yes	132	6,52	2,25	2,11	,036*
	No	147	7,15	2,72		
Affective Cynicism	Yes	132	9,30	2,68	2,43	,016*
	No	147	10,14	3,10		
Organizational Cynicism Level	Yes	132	24,63	6,03	1,99	,047*
	No	147	26,22	7,28		

*p<,05

No significant difference was seen on "cognitive cynicism" sub factor according to $p=,616>,05$. Significant difference was determined between organizational cynicism levels of those with administrative duties ($\bar{X}=6,52$) and without ($\bar{X}=7,15$) of the employees in sports facilities on "behavioral cynicism" sub factor according to $t_{(277)}=2,11$, $p=,036<,05$, between organizational cynicism levels of those with administrative duties ($\bar{X}=9,30$) and without ($\bar{X}=10,14$) of the employees in sports facilities on "affective cynicism" sub factor according to $t_{(277)}=2,43$, $p=,016<,05$, between organizational cynicism levels of those with administrative duties ($\bar{X}=24,63$) and without ($\bar{X}=26,22$) of the employees in sports facilities on general of Organizational Cynicism Scale according to $t_{(277)}=1,99$, $p=,047<,05$.

3.2.4. Organizational Cynicism Levels of Employees in Sports Facilities by Professional Working Years

Organizational cynicism levels of employees in sports facilities by professional working years are given in Table 8.

Table 8: One-Way ANOVA Results Based on the Difference between Cynicism Levels of Employees by Professional Working Years

Sub Dimensions	Occupational Working Year	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F		Post Hoc (Tukey)
					(4-274)	P	
Cognitive Cynicism	Less than a Year	27	9,63	3,62	2,014	,093	
	1-5 Years	86	9,44	3,24			
	6-10 Years	63	9,51	3,19			
	11-15 Years	58	8,45	2,87			
	16 and over	45	8,31	3,06			
Behavioral Cynicism	Less than a Year	27	8,11	2,36	3,20	,014*	1>4, 1>5,
	1-5 Years	86	7,03	2,42			
	6-10 Years	63	6,97	2,61			
	11-15 Years	58	6,28	2,28			
	16 and over	45	6,31	2,72			
Affective Cynicism	Less than a Year	27	10,96	2,36	3,96	,004*	1>5, 2>5
	1-5 Years	86	10,15	3,26			
	6-10 Years	63	9,95	2,27			
	11-15 Years	58	9,21	3,08			
	16 and over	45	8,62	2,82			
Organizational Cynicism Level	Less than a Year	27	29,19	5,86	7,93	,000*	1>4, 1>5, 2>4, 2>5
	1-5 Years	86	27,21	6,78			
	6-10 Years	63	25,68	5,82			
	11-15 Years	58	22,90	6,47			

	16 and over	45	22,91	6,85
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*p<,05 Categories: Less Than One Year=1, 1-5 Years=2, 6-10 Years=3, 11-15 Years=4, 16 and over=5

It is seen that there is no significant difference between organizational cynicism level by professional working years of employees on "Cognitive Cynicism" sub factor according to $F_{(4-274)}=2,01, p=,093>,05$. It is seen that there is a significant difference in organizational cynicism levels according to $F_{(4-274)} = 3,20, p = ,014>,05$ by professional working years on "Behavioral Cynicism" sub-factor. It is seen that there is a significant difference between levels of organizational cynicism by professional working years of employees on "Affective Cynicism" sub-factor according to $F_{(4-274)} = 3.96, p = ,004>,05$. According to the general of organizational cynicism scale, between the organizational cynicism levels by professional working years is significantly different according to $F_{(4-274)}=7,93, p=,000>,05$. This significant difference is due to the fact that organizational cynicism levels of employees who have less than one year of professional seniority ($\bar{X} = 29,19$), organizational cynicism levels of employees who have professional seniority in "1-5 years" ($\bar{X} = 27,21$), organizational cynicism levels of employees who have professional seniority in "11-15 years" ($\bar{X} 22,90$) and organizational cynicism levels of employees who have professional seniority in "16 and over years" ($\bar{X} = 22,91$).

3.2.5. Organizational cynicism levels of employees in sports facilities by income variables

Organizational cynicism levels of employees in sports facilities by income variables are given in Table 9.

Table 9: One-Way ANOVA Results for the Difference between Cynicism Levels on Generic and Sub Factors of the Organizational Cynicism Scale of Employees by Income Variables

Sub Dimensions	Income	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F(4-274)	p	Post Hoc (Tukey)
Cognitive Cynicism	0-1000 TL	32	10,28	3,18	5,74	,000*	
	1001-2000 TL	67	9,81	3,43			1>3,
	2001-3000 TL	83	7,82	2,71			2>3
	3001-4000 TL	71	9,21	3,17			
	4001 and over	26	9,46	2,92			
Behavioral Cynicism	0-1000 TL	32	7,53	2,48	3,30	,012*	
	1001-2000 TL	67	7,43	2,96			1>3,
	2001-3000 TL	83	6,13	2,02			2>3
	3001-4000 TL	71	6,77	2,39			
	4001 and over	26	7,00	2,74			

Affective Cynicism	0-1000 TL	32	11,22	2,64			
	1001-2000 TL	67	9,91	3,32			
	2001-3000 TL	83	9,10	2,74	4,82	,001*	1>3,
	3001-4000 TL	71	10,13	2,89			1>5,
	4001 and over	26	8,50	1,86			
Organizational Cynicism Level	0-1000 TL	32	28,59	6,71			
	1001-2000 TL	67	26,87	8,26			1>3,
	2001-3000 TL	83	23,65	5,16	4,26	,002*	2>3
	3001-4000 TL	71	25,15	6,50			
	4001 and over	26	24,65	5,97			

*p<,05 Categories: 0-1000 TL=1, 1001-2000 TL=2, 2001-3000 TL=3, 3001-4000 TL=4, 4001 and over=5

There is a significant difference between the organizational cynicism levels of employees by income level on "cognitive cynicism" sub factor according to $F_{(4-274)}=5,74$, $p=,000<,05$, between the organizational cynicism levels of employees by income level on "behavioral cynicism" sub factor according to $F_{(4-274)}=3,30$, $p=,012<,05$, and between the organizational cynicism levels of employees by income level on "affective cynicism" sub factor according to $F_{(4-274)}=4,82$, $p=,001<,05$. According to the general of organizational cynicism scale, between the organizational cynicism levels by income level of employees, there is a significant difference according to $F_{(4-274)}=4,26$, $p=,002<,05$. This significant difference resulted from the fact that organizational cynicism levels of employees with income levels of "0-1000 TL" ($\bar{X} = 28.59$) and "1001-2000 TL" ($\bar{X} = 26.87$) being larger.

3. Discussion and Conclusion

Organizational cynicism, one of the prominent concepts with globalization, is negative thoughts and behaviors of the person towards the institution they work for. For this reason, the cynicism levels of the employees should be investigated and these behaviors should be controlled. When the literature is examined, it is seen that organizational cynicism levels of employees are affected by factors such as education, lack of confidence, work experience, working years (Kepoğlu et al 2015, Mısırdalı Yangil et al 2014, Yücel and Çetinkaya 2014, Simha et al 2014, Benerth et al. 2007). While our study found that the dimension of affective cynicism was at the highest level, Mısırdalı Yangil et al. (2014) determined that the affective dimension was the highest level in a similar study they conducted. In our study, age from the demographic variables was affecting affective and behavioral cynicism and seen the highest in the 20-24 age range. The cynicism levels of those who the employees who are married are lower than the

cynicism levels of the single ones. Moreover, it was determined that the levels of behavioral and affective cynicism were lower in the employees without administrative duties, whereas there was no significant difference in the cognitive dimension. Kepoğlu and his colleagues (2015) have also determined that there is a direct proportional relationship between the title and cynicism, similar to our study. We also found that employees who worked less than one year showed more behavioral and affective cynic behavior. It is also seen that the level of cynicism rises as the income decreases.

Cynics go from bad experiences and lose their job motivations and loyalty over time. This situation is also reflected in their work performance. For this reason, the persons in the administrative position in sports facilities should take measures for the causes of cynicism and increase their respect and loyalty to the institution.

Despite the limitations of the research, it is expected that other studies will shed light on the determination of organizational cynicism levels in the sports field.

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